

Bioschemas and Schemas.science at NFDI

Linking research artifacts and communities

Leyla Jael Castro¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3597-8557>,
Nick Juty³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6382-9452>, Phil
Reed³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1219-2137>

¹ ZB MED Information Centre for Life Sciences, Germany

² University of Nantes, France

³ The University of Manchester, UK

⁴ Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany

*Correspondence: Leyla Jael Castro, ljgarcia@zbmed.de

Abstract

Bioschemas [1] is a community-driven initiative aimed to improve the findability of life sciences resources hosted on web pages. It builds upon Schema.org in two ways: (i) providing specific **types** tailored to the life sciences domain, such as BioChemEntity, Protein, and Gene; and (ii) providing recommendation of usage for existing types, aka **profiles**. Bioschemas ‘types’ therefore allows researchers to semantically express biological information, leveraging the system created by search engines. Furthermore, ‘profiles’ build on the limited help provided by schemas.org in the use of their types, by expressing valid property values, marginality and cardinality. In this way, search engines and other services can index the data, with an understanding of the biological context of the data. Adding Bioschemas-compatible structured markup to web pages, ensures that these resources are more accessible and reusable, aligning with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles [2].

Bioschemas markup has been leveraged to combine distributed resources in a federated manner [3], and to create Knowledge Graphs for the Chemical and Plant community in ELIXIR, including partners from the German National Data Research Infrastructure (NFDI) consortia, namely NFDI4Chem and DataPlant [4]. FAIRAgro has also expressed interest in working on a schema.org extension compatible with Bioschemas.

Bioschemas profiles corresponding to cross-domain research artifacts are also exposed on its sister website schemas.science, currently hosting 7 cross-domain profiles: Dataset, DataRepository, ComputationalTool, ComputationalWorkflow, Course, CourseInstance and TrainingMaterial. Schemas.science will facilitate collaborations with partners outside the ‘bio’ domains. The cross-domain and multi-disciplinary nature of research, as seen through emergent ESFRI RIs, is becoming very prominent. Schemas.sci can play an important role, being a central resource and collaborative/hosting space for such work, building out from the ‘exemplar’ community of Bioschemas.

Such a collaborative space would enable a forum to discuss the needs of metadata standards/definitions to enable the bridging of disciplinary boundaries. For instance, there is some interest from the Artificial Intelligence (AI) community to (i) extend the Dataset profile to include as ‘properties’ (elements) from Croissant ML [5] and (ii) create a profile corresponding to the FAIR4ML vocabulary [6]. Croissant ML deals with the description of datasets used in AI approaches, i.e., AI-ready datasets while FAIR4ML aims at describing Machine Learning (ML) models. In addition, training communities (e.g., DALIA [7], TeSS [8] and mTeSS-X), and those related to data and software management plans (e.g., DMP4NFDI [9] and maSMP [10,11]) would also benefit from some core agreements on the usage of schema.org, facilitated through Bioschemas profiles. Bioschemas, together with its sister Schemas.science, aim at making it easier for researchers to implement FAIR for a wide variety of research artifacts, and to make that methodology more consistently implementable in a domain and discipline agnostic manner.

Keywords: Metadata, machine-actionability, schema.org

Resources

- Bioschemas. <https://bioschemas.org> “Bioschemas Website”

Author contributions

Leyla Jael Castro Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Software, Writing – original draft

Alban Gaignard Software, Writing – review & editing

Nick Juty Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – original draft

Helena Schnitzer Project administration, Writing – review & editing

Phil Reed Project administration, Software, Writing – review & editing

Carole Goble Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing

Competing interests

“The authors declare that they have no competing interests.”

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References

- [1] A. J. G. Gray, C. Goble, and R. C. Jimenez, 'From Potato Salad to Protein Annotation', in ISWC Posters and Demo session, Vienna, Austria, Oct. 2017, p. 4. [Online]. Available: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1963/paper579.pdf>
- [2] M. D. Wilkinson et al., 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship', *Sci Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.
- [3] A. J. G. Gray, P. Papadopoulos, I. Mičetić, and A. Hatos, 'Exploiting Bioschemas Markup to Populate IDPcentral', Jun. 22, 2021, OSF. doi: 10.37044/osf.io/v3jct.
- [4] D. Arend et al., 'Bioschemas Resource Index for Chem and Plants', Jan. 31, 2024, OSF. doi: 10.37044/osf.io/yxunp.
- [5] M. Akhtar et al., 'Croissant: A Metadata Format for ML-Ready Datasets', in Proceedings of the Eighth Workshop on Data Management for End-to-End Machine Learning, Jun. 2024, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1145/3650203.3663326.
- [6] L. J. Castro et al., 'FAIR4ML-schema'. Zenodo, Oct. 28, 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14002310.
- [7] J. Geiger, P. Steiner, A. A. Desouki, and F. Lange, 'DALIA Interchange Format', Jun. 07, 2024, Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11521029.
- [8] N. Beard et al., 'TeSS: a platform for discovering life-science training opportunities', *Bioinformatics*, vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 3290–3291, May 2020, doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa047.
- [9] D. Wallace, J. Windeck, K. Diederichs and S. Schönau, "DMP4NFDI - a Basic Service for Data Management Planning", presented at the Base4NFDI User Conference 2024 (UC4B2024), Berlin, Dec. 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14513750.
- [10] L. J. Castro, O. Giraldo, L. Geist, N. Quiñones, D. Solanki, and D. Rebholz-Schuhmann, machine-actionable Software Management Plan Ontology (maSMP Ontology), Jan. 29, 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10582073.
- [11] L. J. Castro, O. Giraldo, L. Geist, N. Quiñones, D. Solanki, and D. Rebholz-Schuhmann, Usage guidance (aka profiles) for the machine-actionable Software Management Plan Ontology, Jan. 29, 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10582121.